

NOTES

Alkali Metal Complexes. Adducts of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with 1,10-Phenanthroline-mono-*N*-oxide

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In this note we report a number of compounds of alkali metal complexes of the general formula $ML.L'$, where $M=Li, Na$ or K ; L =deprotonated acetylacetonone (acac), *o*-nitrophenol (ONP), salicylaldehyde (SalH) or 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ); $L'=1,10$ -phenanthroline-mono-*N*-oxide (PhNO).

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: The usual method of synthesis of the complexes was to add solid 1,10-phenanthroline-mono-*N*-oxide¹ to a suspension of an alkali metal salt (ML) in absolute ethanol in the mole ratio, $ML:L'=1:3$. Larger excess of L' was avoided to prevent its crystallisation in preference to the adduct. All the solids went into solution on stirring and the complexes precipitated almost instantaneously. The contents were warmed for 10–15 min with continuous stirring, when a clear solution was obtained. The adduct crystallised out on cooling was filtered, washed with cold absolute ethanol and dried at 80°.

Elemental analyses and physical data of the ligand and the complexes are presented in Table 1. The infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in the region 4 000–650 cm^{-1} . Molar conductivities of all the complexes were measured in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone at 25° at a concentration of 10^{-6} *M*.

Results and Discussion

The complexes were unstable in aqueous solutions and decomposed slowly in air. However, they were stable under dry condition. The decomposition temperature of all the complexes (except that of $Li8HQ.PhNO$) was higher than the melting point of the ligand, indicating their greater thermal stability.

The free ligand, 1,10-phenanthroline-mono-*N*-oxide (PhNO) showed a strong ir band at 1 650–1 650 cm^{-1} region⁵. The $N-O$ band was observed as a doublet⁶ at 1 269 and 1 249 cm^{-1} ; both these bands shifted to lower frequency by 9–19 cm^{-1} upon complex formation. The 811 and 808 cm^{-1} bands of the ligand assigned to the bending $N-O$ vibrations⁶⁻¹¹, also shifted to lower frequencies by 10–20 cm^{-1} on complex formation. The features of the aforesaid vibrational modes indicated that the ligand PhNO coordinated to the alkali metal ions through the oxygen atom of $N-O$ moiety⁶⁻¹¹ in these complexes. Coordination through the nitrogen atom of the pyridine fragment of the ligand was suggested by frequency shifts

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Conductivity $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				N	M
PhNO	Pale yellow	180*	—	13.20 (13.21)	—
Liacaac.PhNO	Pale yellow	200	10.5	9.27 (9.27)	—
Naacaac.PhNO	Pale yellow	185	12.0	8.80 (8.80)	7.54 (7.23)
LiONP.PhNO	Deep yellow	190	8.5	12.35 (12.32)	—
NaONP.PhNO	Deep yellow	200	10.5	11.76 (11.76)	6.50 (6.44)
KONP.PhNO	Deep yellow	195	12.0	11.30 (11.26)	10.65 (10.45)
NaSalH.PhNO	Light yellow	190	6.8	8.25 (8.23)	6.76 (6.76)
Li8HQ.PhNO	Light yellow	110	8.0	12.20 (12.10)	—
Na8HQ.PhNO	Light yellow	220	8.5	11.56 (11.57)	6.35 (6.34)
K8HQ.PhNO	Light yellow	190	9.5	11.15 (11.08)	10.35 (10.29)

* M.p.

of several bands in the region 1 650–1 540 cm^{-1} associated with the vibrational modes of aromatic amine ring^{5,12-14}.

Molar conductivities of none of these complexes approached either ideal or a 1 : 1 electrolyte¹⁵. Molar conductivities of the present complexes were indicative of their dissociation in *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidone solution.

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Potentiometric Studies on the Complex Equilibria in the Quaternary Systems. Copper(II)/Nickel(II)/Zinc(II)—Picolinic Acid—Oxalic Acid—Catechol

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EXTENSIVE studies have been carried out on ternary¹⁻⁴ systems involving transition metal ions, employing a variety of physicochemical techniques, but much less work has been reported on quaternary system⁵⁻¹⁰. In view of this, it has been considered of interest to investigate quaternary mixed ligand complexes of some of the common metal ions of first transition series of the type,

$M(II)$ -Pic-Ox-Cat, where $M(II) = \text{Cu}^{II}, \text{Ni}^{II}, \text{Zn}^{II}$; Pic = picolinic acid, Ox = oxalic acid, Cat = catechol. Formation constants and free energy of formation have also been evaluated at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 M \text{KNO}_3$) from which the formation constant at zero ionic concentration has been graphically obtained.

Experimental

Stock solutions of metal nitrates were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by the usual methods¹¹. The ligand solutions of Ox, Pic and Cat were prepared by direct weighing. The total volume of the solution (50 ml) and the concentration ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) in metal and ligands were kept constant at the beginning of each titration.

Calculation: The dissociation constants of the ligand were determined by the method of Chaberck and Martell¹². The formation constants ($\log K_{\text{MAB}}$) of the ternary complex MAB formed by the simultaneous addition of A and B to the metal ion, were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa¹³ as extended by Kumar *et al.*¹⁴. $\log K_{\text{MABC}}$ for the quaternary species formed by the stepwise addition of catechol to the initially formed ternary species MAB were evaluated by the method of Thompson and Loraas¹⁵. The overall stability constants of the quaternary complex obtained by summing up the respective values of $\log K_{\text{MAB}}$ and $\log K_{\text{MABC}}$ have been recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Curves for the system Cu^{II} -Pic-Ox-Cat (Fig. 1) have been discussed as representative. The curves and the discussion of the other systems involving $\text{Ni}^{II}/\text{Zn}^{II}$ being identical have been avoided for the sake of brevity. Curves (c) and (d) depicting inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ ($m = \text{moles of the base added per mole of metal ion or ligand}$) represent the titration of Pic and Ox, respectively. No well-defined inflection in the case of cat (curve b) is, however, observed indicating the non-labile nature of phenolic proton. Curves (e), (f) and (g) exhibit the titration of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -Ox/Cat/Pic systems, respectively^{16,17}.

In the systems 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -Pic-Cat (curve h) and Cu^{II} -Ox-Cat (curve i), Pic/Ox acts as primary ligand and the catechol as the secondary one. Thus the ternary complex formation occurs by the stepwise addition of the ligands to the metal ion as is evidenced by the inflections observed at $m=1$ and 3 or $m=2$ and 4 in the respective curves. However, in the system 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -Ox-Pic (curve j), lowering in pH followed by a single sharp inflection at $m=3$ may be attributed to the simultaneous addition of both the ligands to the metal ion forming metal-biligand species. The formation of ternary species is further supported by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curves^{18,19}

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